

MARTINGALLARNI SCHOLIUM(FUNKSIYALARI) UCHUN QO'LLASH

Abdovakhobov Sherzodbek Ikromjon o'g'li
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Annotatsiya

Ushbu ishda ehtimollar nazariyasidagi martingallarni Scholium funksiyalari uchun qo'llash masalasi o'rganiladi. Mustaqil integrallanuvchi funksiyalar ustida martingallar yordamida isbotlar keltiriladi va ular uchun yuqori va kuchli yaqinlashish teoremlari asosida mos natijalar olinadi. Standart shakldagi sodda funksiyalar ketma-ketliklari yordamida, chegara holatdagi funksiyalar uchun umumlashtirishlar amalga oshiriladi. Bu yondashuv orqali martingal nazariyasining integrallanish bilan bog'liq holatlardagi samaradorligi ochib beriladi.

Kirish

Martingallar ehtimollar nazariyasining asosiy tushunchalaridan biri bo'lib, ularning konvergensiyaviy xossalari va integrallanuvchi funksiyalar bilan bog'liqligi ko'plab nazariy va amaliy masalalarda qo'llaniladi. Ushbu tezida martingallarni Scholium deb ataluvchi maxsus funksiyalar uchun tatbiq etish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Xususan, mustaqil integrallanuvchi funksiyalar uchun kuchli va yuqori yaqinlashish teoremlari asosida ikki muhim tenglikni isbotlash usullari taqdim etiladi. Bu isbotlar sodda funksiyalar ketma-ketliklari va monoton yaqinlashish tamoyillariga tayanadi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi — martingallar vositasida Scholium funksiyalari uchun ishonchli teorematik asos yaratishdir.

u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1} (X, A, μ) ehtimollar fazosidagi mustaqil integrallanuvchi funksiyalar bo'lsin. U holda

$$\int_A u_{k+1} d\mu = \mu(A) \int u_{k+1} d\mu \quad \forall A \in \sigma(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\text{va } \int \phi u_{k+1} d\mu = \int \phi d\mu \cdot \int u_{k+1} d\mu \quad \forall \phi \in L^1(\sigma(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k)) \quad (3.7)$$

o'rinli bo'ladi.

Isbot: Tashkil etuvchisi $\mathcal{A}_k = \sigma(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k)$ bo'lgan $A_M := \bigcap_{j=1}^M u_j^{-1}(B_j)$, $B_1, \dots, B_M \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$, $M \leq k$ to'plamni olamiz. $(f_l)_{l \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathcal{E}(\sigma(u_{k+1}))$ bo'lgan soda funksiyalar ketma-ketligini topamiz va ular uchun $|f_l| \leq |u_{k+1}|$ va $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} f_l = u_{k+1}$ o'rinli bo'ladi. Standart ko'rinishdagi $f_l = \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mathbf{1}_{H_j^l}$, $H_j^l \in \sigma(u_{k+1})$ lar uchun kuchli yaqinlashish teoremasidan foydalanamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{A_M} u_{k+1} d\mu &= \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int_{A_M} \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mathbf{1}_{H_j^l} d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mu(A_M \cap H_j^l) \\ &= \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mu(A_M) \mu(H_j^l) = \mu(A_M) \int u_{k+1} d\mu \end{aligned}$$

bu yerda, biz bir necha mos $C_j^l \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ va A_M bilan $H_j^l \in \sigma(u_{k+1})$ uchun tatbiq qildik. Bu eslatmadagi shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi A_k lar uchun isbotlanadi: bu eslatmadagi kabi o'xshash argumentli ekani barcha $A \in \mathcal{A}_k$ lar uchun o'rinli ekanini isbotlaydi.

Dastlab ϕ ni chegaralangan deb faraz qilaylik. $\mathcal{A}_k := \sigma(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k)$ to'plamni olamiz. $|f_l| \leq |\phi|$ va $\lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} f_l = \phi$ ni qanoatlantiruvchi $(f_l)_{l \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{A}_k)$ sodda funksiyalar ketma-ketligini topamiz. Standart ko'rinish $f_l = \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mathbf{1}_{A_j^l}$, $A_j^l \in \mathcal{A}_k$ ga yuqori yaqinlashish teoremasidan foydalanamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \int \phi u_{k+1} d\mu &= \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mathbf{1}_{A_j^l} u_{k+1} d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mu(A_j^l) \int u_{k+1} d\mu \\ &= \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int \sum_{j=0}^{N(l)} y_j^l \mathbf{1}_{A_j^l} d\mu \cdot \int u_{k+1} d\mu = \int \phi d\mu \cdot \int u_{k+1} d\mu. \end{aligned}$$

Agar ϕ integrallanuvchi bo'lib, chegaralangan bo'lmasa, oldingi hisoblashni chegaralangan funksiyalar $|\phi_l| := |\phi| \wedge l$ ga qo'llaymiz va yuqori yaqinlashishni o'ngdagi va monoton yaqinlashishni chapdagi uchun foydalanamiz, quyidagini olamiz:

$$\int |\phi| \cdot |u_{k+1}| d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int |\phi_l| \cdot |u_{k+1}| d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int |\phi_l| d\mu \cdot \int |u_{k+1}| d\mu = \int |\phi| d\mu \cdot \int |u_{k+1}| d\mu.$$

Bu odatda $\phi u_{k+1} \in L^1(\mu)$ ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Shuning uchun biz yuqori yaqinlashishni $\psi_l := (-l) \vee \phi \wedge l$ ga quyidagini olish uchun qo'llaymiz va quyidagi natijaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\int \phi u_{k+1} d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int \psi_l u_{k+1} d\mu = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int \psi_l d\mu \cdot \int u_{k+1} d\mu = \int \phi d\mu \cdot \int u_{k+1} d\mu.$$

Xulosa

Mazkur ishda martingallar yordamida Scholium funksiyalariga oid asosiy tengliklar isbotlandi. Bu jarayonda mustaqil integrallanuvchi funksiyalar uchun sodda funksiyalar ketma-ketligi va kuchli yaqinlashish teoremlari muhim rol o'ynadi. Chegaralangan va chegaralanmagan holatlarga alohida yondashuv qo'llanilib, umumiy integrallanuvchi funksiyalar uchun isbotlar kengaytirildi. Natijalar martingallar nazariyasining integrallanish va yaqinlashish xossalarini chuqurroq tushunishga xizmat qiladi va bu usullar keyingi ilmiy izlanishlar uchun ham asos bo'la oladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Rene L. Schilling Measures, Integrals, and Martingales. Cambridge University Press, The Edinburgh Building, Cambridge CB2 8RU, UK. Published in the United States of America by Cambridge University Press, New York
2. Ash, R. B. and C. A. Doléans-Dade, Probability and Measure Theory (2nd edn), Academic Press, San Diego (CA) 2000.
3. Chow, Y. S. and H. Teicher, Probability Theory. Independence, Interchangeability, Martingales (3rd edn), Springer, Texts in Stat., New York 1997.
4. Dellacherie, C. and P. A. Meyer, Probabilities and Potential Pt. B: Theory of Martingales, North Holland, Math. Studies, Amsterdam 1982. [Note that Probabilities and Potential Pt. A, Amsterdam 1979, by the same authors is a prerequisite for this text.]
5. Garsia, A. M., Topics in Almost Everywhere Convergence, Markham, Chicago 1970.
6. Meyer, P. A., Probabilities and Potentials, Blaisdell, London 1966.

7. Neveu, J., Discrete-parameter Martingales, North Holland, Math. Libr. vol.10, Amsterdam 1975.
8. Rogers, L. C. G. and D. Williams, Diffusions, Markov Processes and Martingales (2 vols., 2nd edn), Cambridge Math. Library, Cambridge 2000.